

CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7269729>

Abstract: The article describes the characteristics of children with hearing impairment, ways and methods of early development. The importance of starting education early, as well as information about the main rules that parents should know about the preschool education of children with hearing impairment.

Key words: Phonetics, communication, speech, intellectual, skills, dactyl speech, deaf pedagogy, character, perception

It is very important to start teaching children with hearing loss early. Pre-school age is an important, one might say, decisive stage in a person's life. During this period, basic habits and skills are formed, character is defined, that is, the foundations of the whole future life are built. At the same time, in the history of deaf pedagogy, there are many examples of people with congenital hearing impairment reaching a very high level of development, communicating freely with hearing people and even learning foreign languages. This was not a miracle. Daily, hourly work, will, faith in success, patience, gentleness, responsibility and love shown by parents and pedagogues allowed these people to achieve so much. There are many examples of people with congenital hearing impairment who have acquired various labor skills even without receiving special education, being illiterate or having low education. Many of them worked in various enterprises, earned the respect of the country, and were awarded state awards. There are people with hearing impairment who have received higher education: engineers, teachers, artists, sculptors. An analysis of cases of high mental development of people with hearing impairment shows that almost always this is the result of early initiation of education. Although the general directions of development of hearing and hearing-impaired children match, deaf and hard-of-hearing children need to be educated in a special school. Deaf and hard of hearing children have a number of characteristics. Them:

- insufficient development in terms of visual perception, including low speed of perception and recognition of objects;
- slow development of imitation, as well as difficulties in choosing an example;
- there is a lack of speech and a deficit of pre-speech communication.

All of the above causes lag in the development of cognitive activity and logical thinking. It is for this reason that it is necessary to pay great attention to the mental education of children with hearing impairment.

A number of tasks of mental education of preschool children can be distinguished:

1. Forming ideas and concepts about the environment.
2. Development of psychological processes of knowledge.
3. Formation of primary methods of intellectual activity.
4. Formation of oral speech.

All the listed tasks should be performed in the process of play, special training and work. Many philosophers and scientists have commented on the importance of early education. Researches of psychologists also prove that goal-oriented, that is, specially organized education from the first days of life is of great importance for human development.

That is why preschool education is considered the first link of the general system of public education, including education of children with hearing impairment. Preschool education is of particular importance for deaf and hard of hearing children, because the difference between hearing and deaf children is not so noticeable in the first period, until about one year of age, until the child's language emerges. Gradually, as the hearing child acquires speech, this difference increases. A child with a hearing impairment does not begin to speak, and his development goes without language, his speech is limited, it is impossible to tell or explain something to the child. He should be specially trained to speak and understand speech. Therefore, the earlier the child is taught to speak, the smaller the difference in his development with the hearing child and the more opportunities for further education. In the kindergarten, deaf teachers and educators teach him everything they teach a hearing child of his age: drawing, gluing, building, counting and even dancing. Like all children, he is taught to work hard, to be neat and polite. In this, many vitally important concepts and skills, which are formed at an early age and are a direct result of education, such as mine-ours, possible-impossible, true-false, begin to be formed.

Teaching a hearing-impaired child to speak is not only teaching him to pronounce sounds, although this is unique in the education of a deaf child and requires special skills, but the main thing is to teach him to understand the content of speech and to use oral speech in communication. , teaching the speaker to understand and speak intelligibly based on the movements of the lips.

It is possible to educate children with hearing impairment at home, but this requires the additional participation of a specialist and requires parents to know the main features of the development and upbringing of a deaf or hard of hearing child, even if the child is placed in a special institution. Parents of a hearing-impaired child need to acquire elementary knowledge of education in order to prepare the child for a special preschool educational institution. For example, the diagnosis is made, there are five months until kindergarten. What if the child gets sick? What if the family is in a remote area with no preschool for deaf children?

Education cannot be delayed. Because, during this period, with every word that a hearing child hears and remembers, the difference between a hearing-impaired child and a hearing child increases.

In order to properly approach the child's education and upbringing, it is necessary to learn the principles of education that form the basis of the recommendations of experts. After mastering them, it will be possible to consciously follow these recommendations in accordance with the child's individual characteristics and living conditions.

Parents should know three important preliminary rules for preschool education of hearing impaired children.

The first. A child with a healthy hearing has no less intellectual development opportunities than a hearing child. Love, combined with a high level of demand and qualified education - these are the conditions that make it possible to realize these opportunities. Believing in success, being able to nurture this belief in a child is an important factor in helping a child

with a hearing impairment to be happy and not to feel his own disability, at least not to suffer from it.

The second. The general issues of education, the education of his feelings, behavior are not secondary to special education, but form the basis of special education. After all, a child, first a child, and then a child with a hearing impairment. It should not be forgotten. his spiritual image, upbringing of his personality - this is the main aspect that determines every situation of special education. In this case, it is necessary to approach the upbringing of the behavior of a child with a hearing impairment in the same way as the upbringing of the behavior of his hearing peers.

The third. It is necessary to use all means to protect the child from being dumb, to teach him to communicate with others. One of the increasingly effective and convenient means (for parents) of teaching a hearing-impaired child is dactyl (finger) speech. He had a hearing impairment at a young age it is widely used in teaching children.

What is digital speech and what is its role in education? The need to use this unusual form of speech in teaching children with hearing impairment is often the cause of objection and opposition from parents.

Dactyl speech is a powerful tool for teaching children with hearing impairment, it can multiply the vocabulary and the quality of speech acquisition, as well as the general level of development of children with hearing impairment. Parents and other people raising children with hearing impairment not only to use it correctly in communication with the child, but also to those whose thoughts, or rather, the judgments they make knowingly, give halal to the full-blooded upbringing of the child. To explain its importance, they must understand the importance of dactyl speech.

Formation of speech is a multifaceted process. It is necessary to develop its various forms, first of all, oral speech, which forms the basis of communication. Formation of pronunciation skills in deaf and hard-of-hearing children is carried out first of all in the form of imitation of an adult, using hearing aids. Activation of the baby's sound reactions is carried out in the process of conducting exercises aimed at supporting these reactions and creating new sounds. These exercises are carried out in the process of communication, when an adult "talks" with a child using various sounds and sound combinations, using them together with gymnastic elements. An important task of working on oral speech of a one and a half to two-year-old child is to form the need for oral speech in the child. Therefore, during games and household activities, an adult names objects, events, toys, actions, and encourages children to imitate their names as much as they can. The most important thing is that the child tries to pronounce sounds, syllables and words following the adult. Imitation of speech is inextricably linked with imitation of actions. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to teaching imitation of body movements. As the child learns to imitate adults, he completes the movements with sounds, syllables, and pronunciation of words. From this period, phonetic rhythmic training begins. Phonetic rhythmicity is one of the main methods of working with children of pre-school age and preschool age on their pronunciation.

Children are taught to react and understand various household noises, natural sounds, and traffic signals at the same time with special exercises aimed at developing auditory perception. Listening to audio recordings also helps in the development of auditory perception. An adult moves with the child to the beat of the music, encourages the child to perform dance movements.

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